

Two newly developed glutinous rice varieties for Assam, India

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We developed high-yielding glutinous rice varieties Kmj 3-292 (Bhogali) and Kmj 3-296-3 (Rongili) from a cross between Ghew Bora, a traditional tall, glutinous rice, and Kmj 1-52-2, a locally developed semidwarf nonglutinous rice. Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3 have been recommended for planting in sali (winter) season in Assam under flood-free, medium to shallow water condition.

Glutinous rices grown in Assam are generally tall, traditional, photoperiod-sensitive varieties with very low yield. Farmers accepted Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3 because of their high yield and grain quality. (See Table 1 for important characteristics of these varieties.)

Kmj 3-292 is a semidwarf with an average height of about 100 cm. Kmj 3-296-3 is a tall (150 cm), stiff-strawed variety. Both were tested at different locations during sali season (Table 2). Average duration to 50% flowering was 129 d for Kmj 3-292 and 133 d for Kmj 3-296-3. Although mid-Jul is the best time for transplanting, these varieties can be planted until Aug (using 60-d-old seedlings) with little effect on normal yield.

Stickiness and acceptable taste are the important characters of glutinous rice in Assam. These high-yielding varieties are compatible with local glutinous rice varieties for stickiness, taste, and cooking time. ■

Table 1. Important characteristics of Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3. Assam, India.

Character	Kmj 3-292	Kmj 3-296-3
Panicle length (cm)	24.2	27.5
Grain length (mm)	9.7	8.4
L:B of grain	4.3	3.1
Kernel length (mm)	6.8	6.1
L:B of kernel	3.50	2.62
1,000-grain wt (g)	25.0	24.8
Husk color	Pigmented	Straw
Kernel color	White	White
Endosperm type	Glutinous	Glutinous
Abdominal white	Opaque	Opaque

Table 2. Grain yield of Kmj 3-292 and Kmj 3-296-3 in various locations, Assam, India.

Location	Year	Yield (t/ha)		
		Kmj 3-292	Kmj 3-296-3	Local glutinous
RARS, Titabar	1985	4.0	3.5	2.6
RARS, Titabar	1988	5.4	3.4	2.8
RARS, Titabar	1989	3.8	3.4	2.6
<i>All India Rice Improvement Project</i>				
Chiplima	1991	4.6	6.0	-
Cuttack	1991	5.7	5.1	-
Karimganj	1991	3.0	3.6	-
Raipur	1991	2.2	2.9	-
Farms (av of 5 locations)	1989	3.3	3.6	2.5

Yield performance of rice hybrids in Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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We evaluated 20 IRRI rice hybrids developed from cytoplasmic male sterile (CMS) lines IR58025 A and IR62829 A at three irrigated locations in Cuu Long Delta. Uniform trials using a randomized block design with three replications were conducted in 1993 dry season. Single seedlings were transplanted at 20- × 20-cm spacing in 8-m² plots. Fertilizer rate was 100-40-30 kg NPK/ha. High-yielding

variety OM90-9 was used as a check.

Yields of hybrids ranged from 1.7 to 6.6 t/ha (Table 1). Low yields of some hybrids were due to high spikelet sterility and hopperburn, caused by brown planthopper. Hybrid IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R was ranked first at two locations and first on average among hybrids studied. It matured in 105 d, 1 wk earlier than the check (Table 2).

Although none of the hybrids showed significant yield advantage over the check, a few promising hybrids, including IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R, IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R, and IR58025 A/IR32358-90-3-3 R, will be evaluated further. ■

Table 1. Yield (t/ha) of rice hybrids at 3 locations in Cuu Long Delta, 1993 DS.

Hybrid	Location			Av
	Omon	Tanhiep	Binhduc	
IR62829 A/IR47310-94-4-3-1 R	5.8	7.3	6.8	6.6
OM90-9 (check)	5.3	6.5	7.4	6.4
IR58025 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	4.9	5.3	7.5	5.9
IR58025 A/IR32358-90-3-3 R	4.8	5.7	6.7	5.8
IR62829A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	5.7	5.0	5.8	5.5
IR62829 A/IR54742-22-19-3 R	4.5	5.0	6.5	5.4
IR58025 A/IR35366-28-3-1-3-2-2 R	4.1	5.5	6.2	5.3
IR58025 A/IR21567-18-3 R	4.7	4.5	6.4	5.2
IR58025 A/34686-179-12-1 R	3.9	4.5	6.5	5.0
IR58025 A/IR19058-107-1 R	3.8	4.9	5.4	4.7
IR58025 A/IR72 R	3.0	5.3	4.9	4.4
IR62829 A/IR32809-26-3-3 R	3.1	4.7	4.7	4.2
IR62829 A/IR44675-101-3-3-2-2 R	3.2	4.0	5.0	4.1
IR58025 A/IR32809-26-3-3 R	3.1	5.3	3.2	3.9
IR62829 A/IR40750-82-2-3 R	3.4	5.1	2.9	3.8
IR62829 A/IR28238109-1-3-2-2 R	2.8	4.9	2.7	3.5
IR58025 A/IR52256-5-2-2-1 R	2.1	3.6	3.8	3.2
IR58025 A/IR35454-18-1-2-2-2 R	1.4	3.3	4.3	3.0
IR58025 A/40750-82-2-2-3 R	1.3	3.4	3.8	2.8
IR62829 A/IR37839-101-1-1-1 R	1.5	1.8	3.5	2.3
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	0.4	1.8	2.9	1.7
LSD (0.05)	1.0	0.7	0.9	